

QUALITY FLAG

REEFTEMPS		NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) RD2 Argo delayed-mode quality control measurement flags http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/					GTSP Quality Flags (Global Temperature and Salinity Profile Programme NCEI NOAA) www.nci.noaa.gov/products/global-temperature-and-salinity-profile-profile-programs/www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Data-Quality-Contro				SEADATANET L20				
code_gtsp	libelle	descriptif	qualite	ID	Preferred Label	Definition ↑	Concept URI	Concept URN	Class	Quality	Description	Comment	conceptid	preflabel	definition
0	No quality control has been performed on this element	Flag 0 data are the level at which all data enter the working archive. They have not yet been quality controlled.	No QC	0	No QC	No delayed-mode quality-control (QC) was performed.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/0/	SDN:RD2:0	Flag 1	No QC	No quality control has been performed on this element	Flag 0 data are the level at which all data enter the working archive. They have not yet been quality controlled.	0	no quality control	No quality control procedures have been applied to the data value. This is the initial status for all data values entering the working archive.
1	The element appears to be correct	NULL	NULL	1	Good data	No adjustment is needed, or the adjusted value is statistically consistent with good quality reference data. An error estimate is supplied.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/1/	SDN:RD2:1					1	good value	Good quality data value that is not part of any identified malfunction and has been verified as consistent with real phenomena during the quality control process.
2	The element appears to be probably good	Flag 2 data are also data in which minor malfunctions may be present but these errors are small and/or can be successfully corrected without seriously affecting the overall quality of the data.	"Probably" good data	2	Probably good data	Delayed-mode evaluation is based on insufficient information. An error estimate is supplied.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/2/	SDN:RD2:2	Flag 2	"Probably" good data	The element appears to be probably good. Flag 2 data are good data in which some features (probably real) are present but these are unconfirmed.	Flag 2 data are also data in which minor malfunctions may be present but these errors are small and/or can be successfully corrected without seriously affecting the overall quality of the data.	2	probably good value	Data value that is probably consistent with real phenomena but this is unconfirmed or data value forming part of a malfunction that is considered too small to affect the overall quality of the data object of which it is a part.
3	The element appears doubtful	Flag 3 data are suspect data in which unusual, and probably erroneous features are observed.	"Probably" bad data	3	Probably bad data that are potentially adjustable	An adjustment may (or may not) have been applied, but the value may still be bad. An error estimate is supplied.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/3/	SDN:RD2:3	Flag 3	"Probably" bad data	The element appears doubtful	Flag 3 data are suspect data in which unusual, and probably erroneous features are observed.	3	probably bad value	Data value recognised as unusual during quality control that forms part of a feature that is probably inconsistent with real phenomena.
4	The element appears erroneous	Flag 4 data are those in which obviously erroneous values are observed.	Bad data	4	Bad data	Not adjustable. Adjusted data are replaced by FillValue.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/4/	SDN:RD2:4	Flag 4	Bad data	The element appears erroneous	Flag 4 data are those in which obviously erroneous values are observed.	4	bad value	An obviously erroneous data value. Data value adjusted during quality control. Best practice strongly recommends that the value before the change be preserved in the data or its accompanying metadata.
5	The element has been changed	Flag 5 data have been altered by a QC Centre, with original values (before the change) preserved in the history record of the profile.	Changed	5	Value changed	Value changed.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/5/	SDN:RD2:5	Flag 5	Changed	The element has been changed	Flag 5 data have been altered by a QC Centre, with original values (before the change) preserved in the history record of the profile.	5	changed value	The level of the measured phenomenon was less than the limit of the measured phenomenon was too large to be quantified by the technique employed to measure it. The accompanying value is the measurement limit for the technique.
6	Reserved for future use	Flags 6 - 8 are reserved for future use.	Reserved						Flags 6 - 8	Reserved	Reserved for future use	Flags 6 - 8 are reserved for future use.		value below 6 detection	The level of the measured phenomenon was less than the limit of the measured phenomenon was too large to be quantified by the technique employed to measure it. The accompanying value is the measurement limit for the technique.
7	Reserved for future use	Flags 6 - 8 are reserved for future use.	Reserved											7 value in excess	The level of the measured phenomenon was too large to be quantified by the technique employed to measure it. The accompanying value is the measurement limit for the technique.
8	Reserved for future use	Flags 6 - 8 are reserved for future use.	Reserved	8	Estimated value	Estimated value (interpolated, extrapolated or other estimation).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/8/	SDN:RD2:8					8	interpolated value	This value has been derived by interpolation from other values in the data object.
9	The element is missing	Flag 9 data indicate that the element is missing.	Element missing	9	Missing Value	Missing value. Data parameter will record FillValue.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/RD2/current/9/	SDN:RD2:9	Flag 9	Element missing	The element is missing	Flag 9 data indicate that the element is missing.	9	missing value	The data value is missing. There should be no

PROCESSING STATES

ReefTEMPS

NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) R06

<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/>

code	libelle	ID	Preferred Label	Definition	Concept URI	Concept URN
0A	RAW DATA	0A	Level 0, class A processing stage	Data are the raw output from instruments, without calibration, and not necessarily converted to engineering units (Level 0). Moreover, no scrutiny, value judgement or intercomparisons were performed on the data; the records are derived directly from the input with no filtering or sub-sampling (Class A).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/0A/	SDN:R06::0A
0B	AUTOMATIC QUALITY CONTROL					
0C	VISUAL CHECK					
1A	CLIMATOLOGY CONTROL APPLICATION OF QUALITY CODE AFTER VISUAL INSPECTION	1A	Level 1, class A processing stage	Data have been converted to values independent of detailed instrument knowledge; automated calibrations may have been done; data may not have full geospatial and temporal referencing, but have sufficient information to uniquely reference the data to the point of measurement (Level 1). Moreover, no scrutiny, value judgement or intercomparisons were performed on the data; the records are derived directly from the input with no filtering or sub-sampling (Class A).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/1A/	SDN:R06::1A
1B	VALIDATED BY PI					
2A	NOT RECOMMEND					
2B	NOT RECOMMEND	2B	Level 2, class B processing stage	Data have complete geospatial and temporal references; information may have been sub-sampled, averaged or compressed in other ways, but no assumptions of scales and variability or thermodynamic relationships have been used in the processing (Level 2). Moreover, the data have been scrutinized and evaluated against a defined and documented set of measures; the process is often automated, and the measures are published and widely available (Class B).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/2B/	SDN:R06::2B
2B+	CALIBRATED DATA	2BP	Level 2, class B, subclass + processing stage	Data have complete geospatial and temporal references; information may have been sub-sampled, averaged or compressed in other ways, but no assumptions of scales and variability or thermodynamic relationships have been used in the processing (Level 2). Moreover, the data have been scrutinized and evaluated against a defined and documented set of measures; the process is often automated, and the measures are published and widely available (Class B). In addition, the measures have been tested on independent data sets for completeness and robustness, and are widely accepted (Subclass +).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/2BP/	SDN:R06::2BP
2C	NOT RECOMMEND	2C	Level 2, class C processing stage	Data have complete geospatial and temporal references; information may have been sub-sampled, averaged or compressed in other ways, but no assumptions of scales and variability or thermodynamic relationships have been used in the processing (Level 2). Moreover, the data have been scrutinized fully including intra-record and intra-dataset comparison and consistency checks; scientists have been involved in the evaluation, and brought latest knowledge to bear; the procedures are published, widely available and widely accepted (Class C).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/2C/	SDN:R06::2C
2C+	CALIBRATED DATA VALIDATED BY PI	2CP	Level 2, class C, subclass + processing stage	Data have complete geospatial and temporal references; information may have been sub-sampled, averaged or compressed in other ways, but no assumptions of scales and variability or thermodynamic relationships have been used in the processing (Level 2). Moreover, the data have been scrutinized fully including intra-record and intra-dataset comparison and consistency checks; scientists have been involved in the evaluation, and brought latest knowledge to bear; the procedures are published, widely available and widely accepted (Class C). In addition, the data are fully quality controlled and peer-reviewed, and are widely accepted as valid; documentation is complete and widely available.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/2CP/	SDN:R06::2CP
3A	AUTOMATIC REDUCED DATA					
3B	CALIBRATED REDUCED DATA	3B	Level 3, class B processing stage	Data have been processed with assumptions about the scales of variability or thermodynamic relationships; the data are normally reduced to regular space, time intervals with enhanced signal to noise (Level 3). Moreover, the data have been scrutinized and evaluated against a defined and documented set of measures; the process is often automated, and the measures are published and widely available (Class B).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/3B/	SDN:R06::3B
3C	GRIDDED REDUCED DATA	3C	Level 3, class C processing stage	Data have been processed with assumptions about the scales of variability or thermodynamic relationships; the data are normally reduced to regular space, time intervals with enhanced signal to noise (Level 3). Moreover, the data have been scrutinized fully including intra-record and intra-dataset comparison and consistency checks; scientists have been involved in the evaluation, and brought latest knowledge to bear; the procedures are published, widely available and widely accepted (Class C).	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R06/current/3C/	SDN:R06::3C

PHYSICAL PARAMETERS

ReefTEMPS

NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) P09
SeaDATANet P09 (MEDATLAS PARAMETER USAGE VOCABULARY)

<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/>

code_roscomp	libelle	unite	ID	Preferred label	Definition	concept URI	concept URN
CNDC	ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY	mho/meter	CNDC	ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY	The degree to which electricity flows through unit length of a water body.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/CNDC/	SDN:P09::CNDC
DOX1	DISSOLVED OXYGEN	ml/l	DOX1	DISSOLVED OXYGEN	Volume of oxygen dissolved per unit volume of the water column.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/DOX1/	SDN:P09::DOX1
DOX3	DISSOLVED OXYGEN	mg/l				http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/DOX3/	SDN:P09::DOX3
FLU2	FLUORESCENCE	milligram/m3	FLU2	FLUORESCENCE	The amount of radiation generated in the water column in response to higher energy radiation transmission expressed as pigment concentration based on a nominal calibration.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/FLU2/	SDN:P09::FLU2
FLUO	FLUORESCENCE	relative unit	FLUO	FLUORESCENCE	The amount of radiation generated in the water column in response to higher energy radiation transmission expressed relative to an unspecified baseline.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/FLUO/	SDN:P09::FLUO
LGHT	LIGHT IRRADIANCE IMMERSER PAR	micromole photon/(m2.s)	LGHT	LIGHT IRRADIANCE IMMERSER PAR	Quantity of visible light photons per unit area per unit time travelling vertically downwards in the water column.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/LGHT/	SDN:P09::LGHT
PHPH	PH	pH unit	PHPH	PH	Minus the log of the hydrogen ion concentration (moles per litre) in the water column.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/PHPH/	SDN:P09::PHPH
PRES	SEA PRESSURE sea surface=0	decibar (1db=10000pascals)	PRES	SEA PRESSURE sea surface=0	The force per unit area exerted by the water column at a point within it.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/PRES/	SDN:P09::PRES
PSAL	PRACTICAL SALINITY	P.S.U.	PSAL	PRACTICAL SALINITY	The quantity of dissolved ions (predominantly salt in seawater) expressed on a scale (PSS-78) based on the conductivity ratio of a seawater sample to a standard KCl solution.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/PSAL/	SDN:P09::PSAL
SSTP	SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE	Celsius degree	SSTP	SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE DEPRECATED		http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/SSTP/	SDN:P09::SSTP
TEMP	SEA TEMPERATURE	Celsius degree	TEMP	SEA TEMPERATURE	The degree of hotness of the water column expressed against a standard scale. Includes both IPTS-68 and ITS-90 scales.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/TEMP/	SDN:P09::TEMP
TUR4	TURBIDITY	N.T.U Nephelo Turb. Unit	TUR4	TURBIDITY	Estimate of suspended sediment concentration based on the proportion of a light transmission in the water column that is reflected back to a co-located receiver	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/TUR4/	SDN:P09::TUR4
VAVH	AVER. HEIGHT HIGHEST 1/3 WAVE	metre	VAVH	AVER. HEIGHT HIGHEST 1/3 WAVE	The average peak to trough height of the highest 1/3 of waves measured during a recording burst	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VAVH/	SDN:P09::VAVH
VDIR	WAVE DIRECTION REL. TRUE NORTH	degree	VDIR	WAVE DIRECTION REL. TRUE NORTH	Direction from which waves are coming relative to True North.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VDIR/	SDN:P09::VDIR
VDSP	WAVE DIRECTION SPREADING REL. Tl	degree				http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VDSP/	SDN:P09::VDSP
VPED	WAVE SPECTRUM PEAK ENERGY DIR	degree	VPED	WAVE SPECTRUM PEAK ENERGY DIR.	Direction towards which the most energetic waves are travelling	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VPED/	SDN:P09::VPED
VPSP	DIR. SPREADING AT WAVE PEAK	degree	VPSP	DIR. SPREADING AT WAVE PEAK	The angle over which the most energetic waves are dispersed.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VPSP/	SDN:P09::VPSP
VSMC	SPECT. MOMENT(0,2) WAVE PERIOD	second	VSMC	SPECT. MOMENT(0,2) WAVE PERIOD	Estimate of mean wave period from (m0/m2) of wave spectrum collected using an accelerometer mounted in a waverider buoy	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VSMC/	SDN:P09::VSMC
VTDH	SIGNIFICANT WAVE HEIGHT	meter	VTDH	SIGNIFICANT WAVE HEIGHT	Significant wave height as estimated by the Tucker Draper method (Draper L. (1963) Proc. Instn> Civ. Engrns. 26 291-304.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VTDH/	SDN:P09::VTDH
VTPK	WAVE SPECTRUM PEAK PERIOD	second	VTPK	WAVE PEAK PERIOD	The period with the maximum wave energy, determined from the wave spectrum.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VTPK/	SDN:P09::VTPK
VTZA	AVER ZERO CROSSING WAVE PERIOD	second	VTZA	AVER ZERO CROSSING WAVE PERIOD	Average of the zero crossing intervals as obtained by dividing the record duration by the number of times the water elevation crosses the mean record level in one direction.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VTZA/	SDN:P09::VTZA
VZMX	MAXI ZERO CROSSING WAVE HEIGHT	metre	VZMX	MAXI ZERO CROSSING WAVE HEIGHT	The largest peak to trough height determined by zero crossing analysis of the demeaned wave elevation recording burst	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/VZMX/	SDN:P09::VZMX
WDIR	WIND DIRECTION REL. TRUE NORTH	degree	WDIR	WIND DIRECTION REL. TRUE NORTH	Direction relative to true north from which the wind is blowing	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/WDIR/	SDN:P09::WDIR
WSPD	HORIZONTAL WIND SPEED	meter/second	WSPD	HORIZONTAL WIND SPEED	Sustained speed of the wind (distance moved per unit time by a parcel of air) parallel to the ground at a given place and time.	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/WSPD/	SDN:P09::WSPD
SLEV	OBSERVED SEA LEVEL	meter	SLEV	OBSERVED SEA LEVEL	The elevation of the sea surface relative to	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/current/SLEV/	SDN:P09::SLEV

PLATFORM TYPES

ReefTEMPS

"NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) L06
"SeaVoX Platform Categories"

<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/>

id	libelle	id	libelle	definition	concept uri	concept urn
1	NOT YET DEFINED	0	unknown	The correct value is not	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/0/	SDN:L06::0
2	RESEARCH SHIP	31	research vessel	A platform of any	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/31/	SDN:L06::31
3	NON-SPECIALIZED SHIP	32	vessel of opportu	A platform for pui	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/32/	SDN:L06::32
4	SATELLITE	68	satellite	A vehicle operating bey	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/68/	SDN:L06::68
5	BALLOON	53	tethered balloon	A container filled with :	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/53/	SDN:L06::53
6	AIRPLANE	62	aeroplane	A fixed-wing self-propo	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/62/	SDN:L06::62
7	ANCHORED BUOY					
8	DRIFTING BUOY	42	drifting surface float	An unmanned instrume	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/42/	SDN:L06::42
9	SUBMERGED FLOAT, ANCHORED	43	subsurface mooring	A collection of oceanog	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/43/	SDN:L06::43
10	SUBMERGED FLOAT, DRIFTING	44	drifting subsurface floa	An unmanned instrume	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/44/	SDN:L06::44
11	FIXED PLATFORM	11	fixed benthic node	A collection of oceanog	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/11/	SDN:L06::11
12	FIXED COASTAL STATION/FIXED SHORE S	17	coastal structure	A fixed man-made struc	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/17/	SDN:L06::17
13	DRIFTING ICE	94	drift ice	Sea ice not conn	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/94/	SDN:L06::94
14	SUBMERSIBLE	20	submersible	A platform operat	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/20/	SDN:L06::20
15	HELICOPTER	67	helicopter	An aircraft without win	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/67/	SDN:L06::67
16	SHORE OBSERVER (AUTO OR FOOT)	71	human	A human being w	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/71/	SDN:L06::71
17	ICE STATION	92	ice shelf	A floating ice she	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/92/	SDN:L06::92
18	GOOSE (AMPHIBIOUS AIRCRAFT)					
19	P2V (AIRCRAFT)					
20	SMALL BOAT	33	self-propelled small bo	A small self-propelled i	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/33/	SDN:L06::33
21	FISHING SHIPS	36	fishing vessel	A platform operating or	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/36/	SDN:L06::36
22	FERRYS	35	vessel of opportu	A platform repea	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/35/	SDN:L06::35
23	TUGS OR WORK BOATS					
24	PRIVATE YACHTS					
25	CHARTER BOATS					

DEVICE CATEGORIES

ReefTEMPS

NERC L05
"SeaDataNet device categories"

<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/>

code_famille	libelle	descriptif	type	ID	Preferred Label	Definition	concept uri	concept urn
BA	BATHY	BATHY	*		157 multi-beam echosounders	Instruments tha	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133157
BF	BATFISH	BATFISH, OBLIQUE CTD TOWS CONVERTED TO VERTICAL TOWS	*		113 fluorometers	Instrument that	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133113
BO	BOTTLE	BOTTLE	B		30 discrete water samplers	A device that cc	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::13330
BT	BATOS	METEO BATOS	*					
DB	DRIFTER	DRIFTER	*		369 hydrophones	Devices contain	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133369
MO	BUOY	MOORED BUOY	*		110 wave recorders	Instrument that	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133110
PF	ALACE	PROFILING ALACE FLOAT	*		134 water temperature sensor	An instrument t	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133134
TK	TRACKOB	THERMOSALINOGRAPH IN REAL TIME	*		133 thermosalinographs	Temperature ar	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133
TR	THERMISTOR	THERMISTOR CHAIN (DELAYED MODE)	*		135 thermistor chains	A group of rigid	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133135
AD	ADCP	ADCP PROFIL	*		115 current profilers	Instrument that	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133115
CM	CM	CURRENT METER	*		114 current meters	Instrument that	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133114
CD	CTD DOWN	CONDUCTIVITY TEMPERATURE DEPTH (CTD) DOWN CAST	C		130 CTD	A reusable instr	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::130
CU	CTD UP	CONDUCTIVITY TEMPERATURE DEPTH (CTD) UP CAST	C		130 CTD	A reusable instr	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::130
CT	CTD	CONDUCTIVITY TEMPERATURE DEPTH (CTD) UP OR DOWN CAST	C		130 CTD	A reusable instr	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::130
MB	MBT	MECHANICAL BATHY THERMOGRAPH	*		390 Mechanical bathythermographs	Tethered probe	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133390
TE	TESAC	CONDUCTIVITY TEMPERATURE DEPTH (CTD) IN REAL TIME	C		131 CTD undulators	An undulating p	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133131
TS	TSG	THERMOSALINOGRAPH (DELAYED MODE)	*		133 thermosalinographs	Temperature ar	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133
XB	XBT	EXPENDABLE BATHY THERMOGRAPH	*		389 Expendable bathythermographs	Disposable, fre	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::389
MG	MG	TIDE GAUGE	*		111 sea level recorders	Instruments tha	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133111
XX	XX	UNKNOWN	*		999 Unknown	The correct ve	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::999
SM	BUCKET	METEOROLOGICAL BUCKET			30 discrete water samplers	A device that cc	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::13330
MP	MULTIPARAMETER PROBE	MULTIPARAMETER PROBE						
PH	PHMETER	PH METER	*		355 pH sensors	Instruments tha	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::133355
WP	PRESSURE SENSOR	WATER PRESSURE SENSOR		WPS	water pressure sensor	Sensors meas	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/	SDN:L05::WPS